

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT - A PRIORITY OF THE ECONOMY

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Abstract

The current state of society can be characterized by various crisis phenomena, which are associated, first of all, with the mechanization of all spheres of human life. Various factors, including technogenic civilization, and industrial society, requiring colossal natural resources, make it impossible for a person to exist only at the expense of natural resources. However, the civilization created by mankind has not yet reached the level at which it could replace the first nature. At present, a person feels less and less a part of nature, and the threat to the vital interests of future generations is becoming more acute and serious. The solution to these problems can be done in only one way - the transition of the whole society to new principles of eco-development, which can result in the emergence of the concept of sustainable development, that is, the harmonious, orderly dynamics of the society in combination with its co-evolution with nature.

None of the states, even the most developed, will be able to embark on the path of sustainable development without fundamentally changing the mechanism of its development without choosing new goals. The new development strategy requires no longer modernization-catching up, but transformational advancement, which will help protect and preserve nature and all of humanity, and not just its part, which seeks to privatize the future to the detriment of other people.

This is because modern world development is associated with an increase in the negative impact on the environment, the depletion of natural resources, and the imbalance of the biosphere. Already today, the consequences of climate change are becoming felt in all corners of the planet. All this leads to an aggravation of social problems and limits the possibilities for further development, and only the implementation of the concept of sustainable development can stop these degradation processes.

Keywords: Technogenic civilization, industrial society, new principles of eco-development.

Introduction

The concept of sustainable development originated in the 1960s and 1970s as a response to the growing global environmental problems. In the same years, many artistic and scientific publications were published, the most significant of which was Garrett Hardin's work "The Tragedy of the Public Domain" and Rachel Carson's novel "Silent Spring". Environmental catastrophes of this period sharpened the understanding of scientists and politicians of the significance and danger of the global environmental problem. At the same time, it was clear that decisions to eliminate this problem could negatively affect economic growth rates, especially in European countries.

The dilemma between further economic development and environmental protection intensified, resulting in the holding of the Stockholm Conference on the Environment in 1972.

Discussion

The principles of the Stockholm Declaration are the basis of the concept of sustainable development. Already in the preamble of the Declaration, the connection between environmental problems and socio-economic backwardness is emphasized, and the most important goal of modern society is highlighted - the protection and preservation of the environment for future generations. One of the significant outcomes of the Conference was the creation of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP).

The Stockholm Conference spurred many countries to adopt legislation to protect the environment. From 1971-1975. 31 national legislative acts are approved in the member countries of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), concerning issues of environmental protection (for comparison: 4 legislative acts for 1956-1960, 10 for 1960-1965, 18 for 1966-1970).

In subsequent years, along with national laws on environmental protection, a wide variety of international environmental documents are adopted. It is worth emphasizing that most of them were limited to the regulation of relations in territories that would not belong to individual states, or concerned primarily with the biophysical aspects of the environment: the conservation of wild animal populations, soil protection, water pollution, and desertification.

In 1980, the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) adopted the World Conservation Strategy, which reflects the need to develop a long-term strategy and joint campaigns for all states. This document was one of the first acts that formed a strategy for solving environmental problems. However, this strategy did not receive adequate support from politicians because the protection of the environment for the authors was a priority issue, and all actions were subordinated to the achievement of this goal. For this reason, to meet the needs of both society and the environment,

the World Commission on Environment and Development, or the Brundtland Commission, is created in 1983.

The commission identified two new problems: ozone depletion and global warming. It was emphasized that the speed of change exceeds the ability of science and society to assess the scale and influence the situation. The Commission concluded that modern institutional capabilities and the level of development in decision-making at the national and international stages do not allow to cope with the problems of sustainable development.

The report of the Commission "Our Common Future" defines the concept of "sustainable development", which, not being a generally accepted international norm, has become widely used and has received a semi-official status. According to this definition, sustainable development is a development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability to meet the needs of future generations.

As in the case of the Stockholm Conference, following the completion of the work of the Brundtland Commission, many national and international agreements concerning the protection of the environment are adopted. One of the first international documents that took into account the principles of sustainable development was the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer. The countries that signed it agreed on the need to stop the use of substances that destroy the ozone layer. This protocol became "epoch-making", as it was a great success - the production of substances harmful to the ozone layer was stopped in developed countries in 1996, and in developing countries - in 2010. [1]

During this period, among scientists who dealt with issues of environmental protection, the ecological version of sustainability began to prevail, which was concluded in achieving a balance between social development and the natural environment. Achieving such a balance requires population reduction or maintenance at the same level and the redistribution of resources from rich countries to poor ones. In this case, the concept of sustainable development acted as an additional political tool in the issue of environmental protection.

In subsequent years, some changes took place in the concept of sustainable development: the creation of favorable living conditions for humans became a priority, and the environment in this case became only a tool to achieve this goal. This change, which began during the work of the Brundtland Commission, was manifested in 1992 at the UN International Conference on Environment and Development in Rio de Janeiro when the Concept of Sustainable Development was officially adopted as the basis for the development of society. [2]

At the beginning of the Declaration, adopted in Rio de Janeiro, it is emphasized that the central place in the concept of sustainable development is occupied by concern for the person. Principle No. 4 states that environmental protection is one of the main conditions for achieving sustainable development. A shift in priorities from environmental protection to human development subsequently in all subsequently adopted documents. [3]

It should be noted several important agreements regarding the protection of the environment were adopted at the conference:

a) The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change is an agreement that obliges countries to direct their efforts toward stabilizing the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere at an acceptable level.

b) The Convention on Biological Diversity is a document calling on the entire world community to rationally use natural components and obtain equal fair benefits from the use of genetic resources.

c) Regulations on the principles of sustainable forest management - a document recommending countries to take an active part in the rational use, conservation, and sustainable development of forests. [7]

In subsequent years, the principles of sustainable development, announced in the Rio Declaration, were confirmed at many other international conferences, among which the following should be highlighted:

1) World Conference on Human Rights in Vienna (1993)

2) Global Conference on the Sustainable Development of Island States in Bridgetown, Barbados (1994)

3) Fourth World Conference on Women's Rights in Beijing (1995)

4) World Food Summit in Rome (1996).

5) UN Conference on Human Settlements in Istanbul (1996)

Special attention should be paid to the signing in 1997 of the Kyoto Protocol to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. It is believed that climate change is driven by economic causes. The Kyoto Protocol calls for the private sector to take the lead by using market mechanisms that encourage the reduction of emissions of harmful substances and encourage investment and technology transfer to developing countries, which would enable them to use more sustainable industrialization patterns. [4]

On January 31, 1999, at the World Economic Forum, UN Secretary-General Kofi Annan proposed to the leaders of large companies to become part of an international initiative - the Global Compact - to unite the efforts of companies initiated by the UN and civil society to implement the ten universal social and environmental principles.

The final change in the original principles of sustainable development occurred at the Millennium Summit in 2000. At the Summit, a Declaration is adopted, emphasizing that prudence is manifested in the rational use of natural resources and living organisms, and only in this way is it possible to preserve natural wealth for future generations. The forum also formulated eight sustainable development goals that were supposed to be achieved by 2015: ensuring environmental security, developing international partnerships for sustainable development, eliminating hunger and poverty, reducing child mortality, developing maternal health, combating HIV / AIDS, malaria, and other diseases, gender equality, empowerment of women, universal primary education.

Regarding the first point, several tasks were highlighted:

- a) inclusion of the concept of sustainable development in state strategies and programs, elimination of processes of a sharp reduction in natural resources;
- b) reducing the scale of biodiversity loss due to a significant reduction in the rate of decline by 2010;
- c) halving by 2015 the proportion of the population that does not have permanent access to clean drinking water and basic sanitation;
- d) to improve the quality of life of at least one hundred million slum dwellers by 2010.

Since the adoption of the MDGs, the work of the UN on sustainable development has been linked to the achievement of precisely these goals, the center of which was the person. Even in tasks aimed at solving environmental problems, the main priority is to improve the life of society. In subsequent years, this situation was only strengthened by new international documents.

Thirty years after the Stockholm conference and ten years after Rio de Janeiro, Johannesburg is hosting the 2002 World Summit on Sustainable Development. If in 1972 the priority was to preserve the environment, in 1992 - to reveal the relationship between environmental problems and the development of society, then the conference in Johannesburg highlights the course towards achieving sustainable development.

The main result of the conference was that three fundamental aspects of sustainable development were clearly articulated: economic development, social development, and environmental protection at the local, national, regional, and global levels.[5]

The results of the Johannesburg meeting received significant support from the world community, however, some organizations accepted it with disapproval. The disappointment was caused by the fact that the participants of this meeting did not make due efforts in setting targets for expanding the use of renewable energy sources. Jonathan Lash, President of the World Resources Institute, noted that the opportunity to increase energy production through the use of non-polluting sources (solar, wind, biomass) and a stable environment for the activities of companies that take measures to reduce emissions are not provided.

It was also disappointing that the Meeting did not result in any binding treaty. Nevertheless, the Secretary General of the Conference, N. Desai, believes that its results have become the basis for the implementation of the decisions made. The plan consists of only fifty pages and is largely targeted and focused. The participants of this meeting agreed on the main directions of activity at the global level, which is the main criterion for its success.

In subsequent years, the concept of sustainable development and environmental issues were considered separately to a greater extent. However, it is worth paying attention to some adopted documents that were aimed at strengthening the environmental aspect of the concept of sustainable development.[6]

In February 2005, the Kyoto Protocol enters into force 90 days after its ratification by Russia. The 2005 Montreal meeting was one of the major events in the

history of climate change negotiations. At this Meeting, it was determined that negotiations would be conducted in parallel both within the framework of the Kyoto Protocol and within the framework of the Convention.

On February 2-3, 2007, on the initiative of the President of France, the Citizens of the Earth Conference was held in Paris, where representatives of the public from 60 countries and leaders of non-governmental organizations took part. At this Conference, a proposal was put forward to create an environmental organization within the UN, authorized to coordinate the necessary environmental protection measures that would be aimed at preserving the Earth for future generations.

The implementation of the concept of sustainable development was also influenced by the global financial crisis of 2008: according to the final Document of the 2009 Conference on the global financial crisis and its Consequences for Development, the crisis caused the emergence or aggravation of serious problems for development in various states.[7]

In 2012, the Conference on Sustainable Development "Rio+20" in Rio de Janeiro. The outcome document, *The Future We Want*, reiterates the concept of sustainable development at the center of sustainable development, while also identifying some of the environmental issues at the intersection of the three pillars of sustainable development: social development, economic growth, and environmental protection. environment. [8] The Framework for Action focuses on the following environmental themes: climate change, oceans, biodiversity, mountains, forests, desertification, energy, sanitation and water, sustainable transport, and sustainable cities and communities.

Nevertheless, environmentalists felt that the final agreement of the Rio +20 conference was ineffective on many points:

from the definition of a green economy and a road map to the initiation of a new negotiating process to create an agreement on the protection of the oceans and institutional reforms of the United Nations regarding environmental issues.

However, it should be taken into account that the inclusion of new environmental themes had an impact on the formation of sustainable development goals after 2015. In December 2014, a summary report of the Secretary-General on the agenda is published, which highlights specific goals that are aimed at protecting the environment, which boil down to the rationalization of the use of water resources (oceans, seas, marine resources) in order to achieve sustainable development), the rationalization of the use of land resources, protective and restoration measures for terrestrial and water ecosystems.[9]

Conclusion

When considering the evolution of the environmental aspect of the concept of sustainable development, one can observe significant changes in the concept itself. In the years of the initial formation of this model, it was the protection of the environment that occupied the first place, and the concept itself acted as a kind of tool to achieve this goal. Subsequently, such components as social and economic development are

introduced into the concept of sustainable development, and the central place is given to the person. At present, the importance of environmental protection, as well as the number of identified environmental problems, in the life of society is increasing, however, unlike in previous years, only aspects that are at the intersection of social and economic development in terms of their impact on living conditions and human activities are in priority.

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